

CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIVEMENT

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION
FOR ACTIVELY PARTICIPATING IN THE JOURNAL

Turanov Akrom Shavkat o'g'li

**KARYERLARDA QO'LLANILADIGAN UZLUKSIZ OQIMLI TEXNOLOGIYA(IQIT) KONSTRUKSIYASINI
O'ZGARTIRISH ORQALI YUK TASHISH UZLUKSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASH**

WILL BE AWARDED FOR THEIR PARTICIPATION IN THE ARTICLE

